

Properties of

$$f_n(A, B) = \{A^{n-1} + A^{n-2}B + A^{n-3}B^2 + \dots + A^2B^{n-3} + AB^{n-2} + B^{n-1}\}$$

n is a prime number greater than or equal to 3.

$A \equiv B \pmod{n}$ and $n \nmid AB$.

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abstract

$f_n(A, B)$ is a multiple of n , but not a multiple of n^2 for all prime number $n \geq 3$.

$$A^n - B^n = (A - B) \times f_n(A, B)$$

I think this theorem could be useful when dealing with polynomials.

So, I will prove this and and write it up as a paper.

Since $A \equiv B \pmod{n}$, we can let

$$\begin{aligned}A &= an + c \\ B &= bn + c\end{aligned}$$

for a suitable natural number c , and for a suitable integer greater than or equal to 0.

$$1 \leq c \leq n - 1$$

Because $n \nmid AB$.

For a natural number $3 \leq r \leq n - 1$,

$$\begin{aligned}A^r &= (an + c)^r \\ &= (an)^r + \binom{r}{1} (an)^{r-1}c + \dots + \binom{r}{r-1} (an)c^{r-1} + c^r\end{aligned}$$

All terms except $\binom{r}{r-1}(an)c^{r-1}, c^r$ are multiples of n^2 .

Therefore it can be expressed by

$$A^r = n^2 \times (\textit{natural number}) + r(an)c^{r-1} + c^r$$

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The same goes for B^q .

$$B^q = (bn + c)^q = n^2 \times (\text{natural}) + q(bn)c^{q-1} + c^q$$

Then let's think about $A^r \times B^q$.

The constant term is always c^{r+q} .

What about the terms of n to the first power?

1. Take $\{r(an)c^{r-1}\}$ from equation A^r and take $\{c^q\}$ from equation B^q and multiply them.

Then we get the term n to the power of 1.

2. Take $\{r(bn)c^{q-1}\}$ from equation B^q and take $\{c^r\}$ from equation A^r and multiply them.

All other terms in the multiplication of $A^r B^q$ are multiples of n^2 .

$$A^r B^q = n^2 \times (\text{natural}) + n\{arc^{r+q-1} + bqrc^{r+q-1}\} + c^{r+q}$$

In $f_n(A, B)$, all terms $A^r B^q$ are maintain

$$r + q = n - 1$$

And $f_n(A, B)$ is the form of

$$f_n(A, B) = \sum_{r=0}^{n-1} \{A^r B^{(n-1)-r}\}$$

Let's just focus on the first power terms of n .

$$\begin{aligned}
 A^{n-1} &= (n-1)(an)c^{n-2} \\
 A^{n-2}B &= (n-2)(an)c^{n-2} + 1(bn)c^{n-2} \\
 A^{n-3}B^2 &= (n-3)(an)c^{n-2} + 2(bn)c^{n-2} \\
 A^{n-4}B^3 &= (n-4)(an)c^{n-2} + 3(bn)c^{n-2} \\
 &\vdots \\
 A^3B^{n-4} &= 3(an)c^{n-2} + (n-4)(bn)c^{n-2} \\
 A^2B^{n-3} &= 2(an)c^{n-2} + (n-3)(bn)c^{n-2} \\
 AB^{n-2} &= 1(an)c^{n-2} + (n-2)(bn)c^{n-2} \\
 B^{n-1} &= (n-1)(bn)c^{n-2}
 \end{aligned}$$

If we add up all the terms above, it is equal to the sum of the first power factors of n in $f_n(A, B)$

$$= \sum_{r=0}^{n-1} \{A^r B^{(n-1)-r}\}$$

So the first power factors of n in $f_n(A, B)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(an)c^{n-2}\{(n-1) + (n-2) + \dots + 2 + 1\} \\
 &+ (bn)c^{n-2}\{1 + 2 + \dots + (n-2) + (n-1)\} \\
 &= (an)c^{n-2} \times \frac{(n-1)(n)}{2} + (bn)c^{n-2} \times \frac{(n-1)(n)}{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since n is a prime number that $n \geq 3$, $\frac{(n-1)(n)}{2}$ is a multiple of n .

Therefore this result is a multiple of n^2 .

In summary,

$$\begin{aligned} f_n(A, B) &= n^2 \times (\text{natural number}) + (\text{first order equation for } n) \\ &+ (\text{constant term}) \end{aligned}$$

$$(\text{first order equation for } n) = n^2 \times (\text{natural number})$$

Therefore, we only need to consider the constant term.

In $A^r B^q$, the constant term was always c^{r+q} .

Since $(r + q) = n - 1$ in $f_n(A, B)$,

c^{n-1} is added as many times as the number of terms of $f_n(A, B)$.

The number of terms in $f_n(A, B)$ is n .

As a result,

$$f_n(A, B) = n^2 \times (\text{natural number}) + n \times c^{n-1}$$

Since $c \leq n - 1$ and n is a prime number, $n \nmid c^{n-1}$,

$f_n(A, B)$ is a multiple of n , but not a multiple of n^2 .

Now that I look at it, I see that this property also holds for all odd exponents n greater than 3.

Thank you for reading.

